

Digital Audio: A guide to good practice

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Contents

- 1. Introduction to digital audio 5
 - 1.1 What is digital audio? 5
 - Areas of application 5
 - 1.2 Things to consider 6
- 2. Things to consider when creating digital audio 7
 - 2.1 General considerations 7
 - Containers and codecs 7
- 3. Archiving digital audio 9
 - 3.1 Deciding what to archive 9
 - 3.2 Deciding how to archive 9
 - Significant properties 9
 - Recommended file formats 10
 - 3.3 Metadata and documentation 11
- 4. Format for audio 12

Digital audio: a guide to good practice

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1. Introduction to digital audio

Since recorded audio is such an integral part of modern society, we may not always realize how vulnerable it is to degradation and loss. Since the late 19th century, recording and playback methods have been experimented with and improved, and over time a range of different storage media have been developed. As a result, there are now many types of audio format in both personal and institutional collections throughout the world. While some formats are more durable than others, all are at risk. For the preservation of audio data, it is therefore essential to know the differences between different formats, such as their strengths and weaknesses.¹

This guide aims to provide guidance on what to consider when preserving the digital audio. The guide covers the most common file formats used for storing audio files and the formats that are suitable for archiving. It will also review the archiving strategies that can be used to ensure that the quality of the audio files is maintained after preparation for archiving. The guide does not provide detailed information about the physical properties of audio, or the ways in which recorded sound can be manipulated on a computer or via a mixing desk. The guide will also not suggest strategies for archiving analogue audio, or audio stored on physical storage media.

1.1 What is digital audio?

Digital audio may be described as the technology used to record, store, generate, manipulate, and reproduce audio using audio signals that have been encoded in digital form. In simple terms, the process may be described as a microphone picking up sound and converting it into an analogue electrical signal. An analogue-to-digital converter (ADC, AD or A/D for short) then transforms the analogue signal into a digital signal. When the sound wave is converted into digital audio, the analogue signal is sampled. Sampling simply means taking a sample of something and this is what happens here. Measurements are taken at regular intervals of a few microseconds and a value is recorded at each given moment.² The more values are recorded, the better the reproduction becomes. If you have a sampling frequency of 44.1 kHz (which is common for CDs), then you are taking 44,100 measurements (samples) per second.³ The digital signal, or digital audio, can then be edited and manipulated using digital audio tools. Then, when the recording is to be listened to, a digital-to-analogue converter performs the reverse process, transforming the digital signal back into an analogue signal that is sent to the headphones or speaker.

Areas of application

Digital audio is used in many research fields and for different purposes. There is good reason to preserve audio from our culture for future generations; recordings serve as an ethnographic record of the spoken word, musical traditions, stories, and songs from cultures around the world and from different times. For example, recordings allow linguists to study the grammar and vocabulary of both living and extinct languages and dialects.⁴ Recorded interviews are also used, for example in connection with surveys. The advantage, compared to paper questionnaires, is that complicated questions can be asked, and the interviewer can explain if there are misunderstandings. A recorded interview contains nuances that cannot be stored or preserved in text, and there is good reason to preserve such a recording so that it can be reused in the future. In historical research fields such as

¹ <https://www.clir.org/pubs/reports/pub164/pub164.pdf> (p. 2). Accessed 12 August 2022

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pulse-code_modulation. Accessed 22 February 2023

³ <https://www.digitizationguidelines.gov/term.php?term=samplingrateaudio> Last visited 22 February 2023

⁴ <https://www.clir.org/pubs/reports/pub164/pub164.pdf> (p. 2). Accessed 12 August 2022

archaeology and history, the use of audio as a medium is less widespread. Where digital audio files are created, it is often as part of projects to record oral tradition or to recreate 'archaeological sounds', for example through the reconstruction of musical instruments, or to record sounds in an archaeological context (for example by virtually or physically recreating a church, an area of earthworks, etc.).

1.2 Things to consider

It is important to know that analogue audio signals are sensitive to noise, hum and distortion from electronic circuits and associated hardware. Interference that is recorded will also be present in the finished product and throughout the preservation process unless noise reduction software is used. Post-processing noise reduction can be a both complicated and time-consuming process and the quality of the results varies. For the sake of audio quality, it is therefore recommended to troubleshoot as a preventive measure to find the source of any interference and remove it (for example replace a bad cable) before recording.

2. Things to consider when creating digital audio

As with digital images and video files, digital audio files contain a number of important properties that affect the quality and size of the audio file and are directly related to the file format chosen. This guide aims to provide an overview of digital audio files but does not cover either the digitization of material or the transfer of digital tapes or CD/DVD based audio to desktop format. As with other data types included in the SND guides, it is emphasized that data are best preserved on network-attached storage rather than on physical media such as magnetic tapes, CDs, and DVDs.

2.1 General considerations

A digital audio file that is intended to be preserved should ideally be encoded and stored in an uncompressed file format, but uncompressed files are often very large. Therefore, if necessary (for example in the event of a lack of storage space), a non-destructive, compressive codec such as Flac can be used (more on this in the chapter *Containers and codecs*).⁵ On account of the wide range of formats and codecs, it is important to have detailed technical metadata describing the data file. Metadata are also essential for documenting the creation of the file (for example location, date, people involved). The other information that needs to be included is covered in more detail later in the guide.

Containers and codecs

It can be difficult to distinguish between containers⁶ and codecs. The distinction between them is somewhat blurred, partly due to a general lack of standardization and a large number of file extensions.

Unlike file formats for other types of data (for example for text or images), many of the digital audio formats are in fact container formats. In simple terms, container formats make life easier for the user by packaging many types of data in one file (audio, image, video, metadata, etc.), instead of there being one file for each type of data. A simple container format may contain different types of audio format, while a more advanced container format may support multiple audio and video streams, subtitles, chapter information and metadata (tags), as well as the synchronization information needed to play the different streams together.

A codec is a programme that encodes and decodes digital data streams or signals in different ways. Its task is normally to compress and unpack data so that files with a smaller file size can be stored and transferred. In simple terms, compression is achieved by removing sounds that are not normally heard, but at the risk of losing some of the dynamics. Therefore, it is essential for the data creator to be aware of the exact codecs used, their capacity and their intended use. There are codecs that preserve the audio file in its original state, either completely uncompressed or with lossless

⁵ <https://www.clir.org/pubs/reports/pub164/pub164.pdf> (p. 111). Accessed 15 August 2022

⁶ A container or wrapper format is a metafile format, the specifications of which describe how different data elements and metadata coexist in a data file. Since the container does not describe how the data or metadata are encoded, there is a risk that a programme that identifies and opens container files will not be able to decode the stored information. One reason for this could be that the programme lacks the necessary decoding algorithm. By definition, container formats can contain any type of data. Although there are some examples of such more general file formats (for example Microsoft Windows DLL files), most container formats are specialized for specific data requirements. A popular branch of containers is those used for file formats used in multimedia. Audio and video streams can be encoded and decoded using many different algorithms, and a container format is used to provide data creators and users with a single file format.

compression. There are also codecs that use destructive compression. Destructive compression means that some of the information is lost, and the file becomes smaller in size. While it may seem drastic to choose a codec that irreversibly degrades the quality of the audio file, the degradation may not be audible to the listener of the recording. However, from a long-term perspective, it is recommended to create and preserve an audio file with the highest possible quality and in an uncompressed format. Compressed datasets can then be created from this dataset.

Which codec?

If you want to find out which codec is used, you can do so in the free programme MediaInfo.⁷ MediaInfo provides technical information about video and audio files. In addition to the codec, you will be told what metadata are associated with the file.

You can also find out the codec in the open source programme VLC Media Player.⁸ To do this, open the audio file in VLC, click the *Tools* button and go to *Codec Information*.

To ensure that a created audio file is of sufficiently high quality, the creator should be aware of:

- the relationship between audio container and codec, and their respective quality. Containers are what we usually equate with file formats.
- the fact that, as part of a codec, the audio format may consist of uncompressed and compressed formats. The latter may be with or without data loss, which may affect the quality of the audio file.
- that many file formats allow metadata to be embedded in the container format, which may be something the data creator wants to use to document important aspects of the creation of the data material. It is important to flag the existence of metadata so that they can be preserved regardless of file format.
- what rights apply to the format. This is particularly true in interview situations, where different laws may apply to protect the individual (for example the Swedish Data Protection Act).

⁷ <https://mediaarea.net/sv/MediaInfo>. Accessed 15 August 2022

⁸ <https://www.videolan.org/vlc/>. Accessed 12 August 2022

3. Archiving digital audio

3.1 Deciding what to archive

If one or more files are saved with original audio data, they should be preserved in a format that captures and preserves the properties of the recording in an equivalent or better format than the original. The original files must be preserved in their unprocessed state. The only exception is any cuts at the very beginning and end of the audio file if there are silent parts there.⁹ This is because uncompressed audio formats encode audio and silence in the same way, with the result that silent parts of a recording require the same storage space as parts with audio. Apart from the physical characteristics of the file, associated metadata and other documentation (embedded in or stored separately) must be preserved and maintained. The final product, i.e., the fully processed audio file (with metadata), should also be preserved in a format equivalent to or better than the original. The reason for preserving both the original files and the processed, finished audio file is that the latter is likely to lack audio data contained in the original file. For example, it could be a two-hour interview that has been cut to twenty minutes in the final recording. In addition, a processed audio file may consist of a merger of several audio tracks or audio files (as in the case of music recordings, where each audio track may correspond to an instrument). If this is the case, the data creator has to assess whether there are audio data in the file that does not appear to their best advantage and need to be treated separately. If the original file and the processed file are similar and the processed file contains all the information deemed important for future reuse, it is sufficient to keep only the finished audio file.

3.2 Deciding how to archive

It is no longer practical, or financially justifiable, to archive analogue copies of audio recordings to preserve their content. High-quality analogue recording equipment and the spare parts needed to maintain the functionality of existing equipment are both expensive and increasingly difficult to obtain. Analogue copies lose quality with each generation, while a copy of an uncompressed digital audio file can be identical to the digital original. Archiving audio recordings as digital files enhances accessibility and is recommended. However, physical storage media such as CDs and DVDs are not suitable for archiving.¹⁰ All the same, all digital file formats are at risk of becoming obsolete and falling out of use in the future. If this happens, future programmes will not be able to read and present the information in the files correctly, and valuable research data may be lost. It is therefore important to use file formats that are very likely to be usable in the future. If there is a need to convert a file from one format to another, several important properties of the audio file need to be known to minimize the risk of data loss.

Significant properties

The significant properties of an audio file that should be maintained throughout the preservation process are, in brief:

- Duration – i.e., the length of the audio file in Timecode Character Format (TCF). Checks should be made to ensure that the file matches the intended length.

⁹ <https://www.clir.org/pubs/reports/pub164/pub164.pdf> (p. 112). Accessed 15 August 2022

¹⁰ http://www.arsc-audio.org/pdf/ARSCTC_preservation.pdf (p. 2). Accessed 12 August 2022

- Bit depth – indicates how many bits of information are stored per sample and is an indicator of audio quality (for example 16 or 24 bits).
- Sample rate – an indicator of the number of samples per second. The sample rate is usually expressed in hertz, for example 44.1 kHz (a common sample rate) and, like bit depth, it is an indicator of the quality of the file.
- Channels – describes the number of streams used to carry the sound to the speaker. Mono (one channel), stereo (two channels) and surround (more than two channels, often 5.1 or 5.2).
- Audio channel assignment – if each channel has been assigned a channel number, the data creator can select where the audio of different channels will come from. For example, in a stereo recording of an interview, it would be possible to decide that the audio track with the interviewer is assigned to channel 1 and is heard in the left speaker and the audio track with the respondent is assigned to channel 2 and is heard in the right speaker.¹¹

Recommended file formats

The file formats described below are those recommended for preserving audio files:

Format	Description
Waveform Audio (.wav)	Recommended for preservation of uncompressed audio (PCM12). The format can also be tagged with metadata and can embed metadata in XMP format.
Broadcast Wave Format (BWF) (.bwf .wav).	Recommended for preservation, BWF also extends the WAV format with an extra bit for metadata, but users should be aware that compatibility between WAV and BWF files can be problematic, especially when migrating from WAV to BWF.
Audio Interchange File Format (.aif, .aiff)	Suitable for preservation when used to store uncompressed PCM audio files. The format can store embedded metadata.
FLAC (.flac)	An open, lossless compression codec, suitable for preservation when uncompressed audio is not desired.
Matroska (.mka)	Matroska is a flexible, free container format suitable for archiving, but depending on the codec used. Intended primarily for multimedia files containing both audio and video.

¹¹ <http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/Main>. Accessed 12 August 2022

¹² <https://wiki.multimedia.cx/index.php?title=PCM>. Accessed 12 August 2022

3.3 Metadata and documentation

Metadata may either be in an accompanying separate file or embedded in the audio file itself. The metadata elements listed below mainly describe technical aspects. The items below marked with * are necessary properties that *must* be included in the description. Others are more general and *should* be recorded.

Properties	Description
Software*	Programme (or device) used to create the file.
File size*	The size of the file
File format*	The format in which the file is saved (see Chapter 4. <i>Containers</i>)
Bit depth*	For example, 16 or 24 bits.
Sample rate (kHz)*	For example, 44.1 kHz (kilohertz).
Codec*	The codec used to create the file, for example FLAC or AAC.
Length of recording*	Preferably given in hours, minutes, seconds (hh:mm:ss).
Copyright*	Who owns the file and how may it be used? Might it contain sensitive personal data? This is very important for audio files, especially oral histories/interviews.
Transcripts of interviews	Transcripts of interviews can be important documentation, particularly to clarify who is involved in the recording and to facilitate identification of individuals.
Context	If the recording was originally retrieved from some form of physical storage media, contextual information such as 'B-side of LP XXX' or 'track 3 of CD XXX' is needed. ¹³
Bit rate	Should be recorded and is often specified in kbps.

¹³ <https://www.clir.org/pubs/reports/pub164/pub164.pdf> (p. 115). Accessed 15 August 2022

4. Format for audio

The tables below describes some common file formats used for storing digital audio. Some of these formats may appear obsolete, but they are described here because it may be necessary to handle older file formats. The associated software for file formats and how, or whether, it can be used for archiving is also covered.

Advanced Audio Coding	
File format/ extension	AAC/ .aac
Format	An ISO standard format based on the MPEG-2 and MPEG-4 formats.
Container/codec	Codec
Description	The format is widely supported by a number of common devices (Wii, PlayStation, iPod, iPhone, and Android, among others) and is designed to be the successor to the MP3 format but provides better sound quality than <i>MP3</i> . The AAC data format is often packaged in MP4, 3GP, ADIF, and ADTS container formats.
Recommendations	Suitable for dissemination, but not suitable for archiving.

Audio Interchange File Format	
File format/ extension	AIFF/ .aif, .aiff
Format	A proprietary file format developed by Apple, similar to the Wave format.
Container/codec	Container
Description	As with .wav, .aiff is mainly used to store uncompressed PCM audio files (AIFF_LPCM). The format can also store metadata along with audio in other compressed codec formats.
Recommendations	Suitable for preservation in uncompressed format. The format is mainly used by Apple users while Windows users usually use .wav, which works just as well.

Audio Video Interleave	
File format/ extension	AVI/ .avi
Format	A proprietary, ¹⁴ binary, ¹⁵ container format for both audio and video developed by Microsoft.
Container/codec	Container
Description	<p>A common container format that supports a number of codecs but has some limitations due to old specifications: it cannot reliably contain certain types of variable bit rate (VBR) data¹⁶ (for example MP3 with sample rates below 32 kHz) and does not have a standardized way of encoding information about image proportions, so playback software does not automatically detect the proportions.¹⁷</p> <p>The format originated in the Resource Interchange File Format (RIFF). According to the RIFF format, the AVI container consists of three parts: The first part, the header labelled <i>hdrl</i>, contains metadata about the file (width, height, fps, etc.). The second part, labelled <i>movi</i>, contains a number of packets of video and audio data in almost any type of compression. The third optional part, labelled <i>idx1</i>, indexes any offsets (amplitude and time/phase shifts of the audio) contained within the various parts of the AVI file.^{18, 19}</p>
Recommendations	Works for dissemination, but not suitable for archiving.

Broadcast Wave Format (BWF)	
File format/ extension	BWF/ .bwf, .wav
Format	The file format was developed by the European Broadcasting Union (EBU) and is an extension of the WAV format.

¹⁴ **Proprietary** software is software that has restrictions (usually set by the owner) on using, modifying, or copying it.

¹⁵ **Binary file**, a file containing data in a format intended to be read by specific computer programmes, with a substantial portion of the information encoded as other than text. Binary files generally cannot be interpreted without knowledge of the file format, except possibly to some extent.

¹⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Variable_bitrate. Accessed 12 August 2022

¹⁷ <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/fdd/fdd000059.shtml>. Accessed 15 August 2022

¹⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Audio_Video_Interleave. Accessed 12 August 2022

¹⁹ <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/fdd/fdd000059.shtml>. Accessed 15 August 2022

Container/codec	Container
Description	Broadcast Wave Format consists of uncompressed audio and is based on <i>the</i> WAV format but has been extended with an extra bit for metadata. Although they are based on the same format, compatibility between WAV and BWF files can be problematic, especially when migrating from WAV to BWF. The purpose of the file format is precisely the additional metadata that facilitate the transfer of audio data between different applications. Specifying the metadata format used also allows synchronization with other recordings. There are three specifications. The latest (version 2) was released in 2012. ²⁰
Recommendations	Suitable for archiving using LPCM encoding (WAVE_BWF_LPCM_2). ²¹

FLAC

File format/extension	FLAC/ .flac
Format	FLAC (Free Lossless Audio Codec) is an open, free, non-destructive compression codec developed by the Xiph.Org Foundation.
Container/codec	Codec
Description	FLAC was developed as a lossless, more efficient open source alternative to the MP3 format and has grown in popularity. FLAC-encoded audio can be embedded in various container formats including 'Native Flac' and Ogg.
Recommendations	Suitable for dissemination and can be used as an archive format where compression is required. For uncompressed audio, there are better formats.

Matroska Multimedia Container

File format/extension	Matroska/ .mka (audio), .mkv (video), .mk3d (3D video)
Format	An open standard container format, free to use, but with some parts licensed under GNU LGPL. ^{22 23}

²⁰ <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/fdd/fdd000357.shtml>. Accessed 15 August 2022

²¹ <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/fdd/fdd000359.shtml>. Accessed 15 August 2022

²² <https://www.gnu.org/licenses/lgpl.html>. Accessed 12 August 2022

²³ <https://www.matroska.org/>. Accessed 12 August 2022

Container/codec	Container
Description	Matroska is a flexible, cross-platform container format for multimedia. The format can contain any number of video, audio, image, or subtitle files in a single file and aims to be the open source alternative to existing proprietary containers such as AVI, ASF, MOV, RM, MP4, and MPG ES. ²⁴
Recommendations	Suitable for dissemination and archiving, depending on the codec used. For video preservation, be aware that Matroska_FFV1 does not yet support timecode, so you should not use the format for timecode video. This function is still in development. ²⁵

MPEG	
File format/extension	MPEG-1/ .mpg, .mpeg
Format	Open standard, binary format for video and audio. Destructive (lossy) compression, but without destroying the quality significantly.
Container/codec	Codec
Description	An international ISO/IEC standard (11172) ²⁶ developed by the Moving Picture Experts Group (MPEG) for Video CD (VCD and SVCD) and the less common DVD-Video. Provides reasonable quality for audio/video playback comparable to VHS tape. Many tools, including open source tools, are available to work with this format. Works well for video at speeds up to 1.5 Mbps. ²⁷ MPEG-1 Audio Layer III is the same as MP3 but is a sub-format of MPEG-1. MP3 is a destructive codec that also allows metadata (ID3) to be embedded in the file. The format is perhaps the most common standard for music files on the internet. MP3 is supported by most media players. The MP3 format was further developed as MPEG-2.
Recommendations	Works for dissemination and archiving. ²⁸ However, if the file was originally created in a better quality format, it should be saved in that format (depending on the format).

²⁴ <https://www.matroska.org/technical/whatis/index.html>. Accessed 12 August 2022

²⁵ <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/fdd/fdd000342.shtml>. Accessed 15 August 2022

²⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/25371.html>. Accessed 12 August 2022

²⁷ <http://www.digitalpreservation.gov/formats/fdd/fdd000035.shtml>. Accessed 12 August 2022

²⁸ However, the Library of Congress' Packard Campus for Audio-Visual Conservation recommends [MPEG-2, Main Profile](#) (lossless JPEG 2000 wrapped in MXF operational pattern 1a) for archiving.

File format/ extension	MPEG-2/ .mpg, .mpeg
Format	Open standard
Container/codec	Codec
Description	As with MPEG-1, an ISO/IEC standard (13818), ²⁹ but for DVD and digital TV. ³⁰ It contains a number of different profiles (Simple Profile, ³¹ Main Profile, ³² and 4:2:2 profile, ³³ the last of which is used for digital TV), all of which contain different standard specifications for elements such as screen size and data rate. MPEG-2 video is not optimized for low bit rates (i.e., less than 1 Mbps) but provides superior quality compared to MPEG-1 at rates above 3 Mbps.
Recommendations	Recommended for archiving.
File format/ extension	MPEG-4, version 2/ .mp4
Format	An ISO standardized format.
Container/codec	Container
Description	<p>The MPEG ISO/IEC standard (14496-10) is adapted for the web (streaming media), voice (videophone) and TV broadcasting, all of which benefit from compressing the AV stream. Based partly on Apple's QuickTime .mov format, it has MPEG-4 at its core for audio and video, but also supports 3D objects, text, <i>sprites</i>, and other types of media to allow interactive elements to be included. As with MPEG-2, MPEG-4 contains two main versions and a large number of profiles optimized for different purposes.³⁴</p> <p>MPEG-4 part 10 (ISO/IEC 14496-10:2020³⁵) is technically equivalent to the International Telecommunication Union standard ITU-T H.264: Advanced Video Coding.³⁶ The codec is one of the video encoding formats for Blu-Ray and for HDTV broadcasting in Europe.</p> <p>MPEG-4 part 14 (ISO/IEC 14496-14:2020³⁷) is a commonly used container format that supports, among other things, a number of different audio codecs</p>

²⁹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/75928.html>. Accessed 12 August 2022

³⁰ <http://www.digitalpreservation.gov/formats/fdd/fdd000335.shtml>. Accessed 12 August 2022

³¹ <http://www.digitalpreservation.gov/formats/fdd/fdd000033.shtml>. Accessed 12 August 2022

³² <http://www.digitalpreservation.gov/formats/fdd/fdd000032.shtml>. Accessed 12 August 2022

³³ <http://www.digitalpreservation.gov/formats/fdd/fdd000034.shtml>. Accessed 12 August 2022

³⁴ <http://www.digitalpreservation.gov/formats/fdd/fdd000155.shtml>. Accessed 12 August 2022

³⁵ <https://www.iso.org/standard/75400.html>. Accessed 12 August 2022

³⁶ <https://www.itu.int/ITU-T/recommendations/rec.aspx?rec=14659&lang=en>. Accessed 12 August 2022

³⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/79110.html>. Accessed 12 August 2022

	(for example AAC, MP3) as well as embedded metadata (including XMP). Most video playback applications support MP4. MP4 files can contain a number of audio, video, and subtitle streams.
Recommendations	MPEG-4 works for archiving and dissemination, but higher quality MPEG formats should be used where possible.

Ogg Vorbis	
File format/extension	Ogg/ .ogg
Format	A generic open format developed by the Xiph.Org Foundation.
Container/codec	Codec
Description	Vorbis codec was developed as a completely open alternative to the MP3 format, primarily as a format for file distribution. Vorbis has some varied uses. For example, many computer games use Vorbis to store their audio files. Wikipedia uses Vorbis. Ogg Vorbis ³⁸ should not be confused with the Ogg container format (the Ogg container format may contain codecs other than Vorbis, for example FLAC, Opus or Speex). ³⁹
Recommendations	Suitable for dissemination, but not suitable for archiving.

Opus	
File format/extension	Opus/ .opus
Format	An open, free audio compression format developed by the Xiph.Org Foundation.
Container/codec	Codec

³⁸ <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/fdd/fdd000117.shtml>. Accessed 16 August 2022

³⁹ <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/fdd/fdd000026.shtml>. Accessed 16 August 2022

Description	The format is designed specifically for real-time applications that communicate over the internet. Opus can seamlessly scale to high and low bit rates and adapt its properties to prevailing conditions such as a poor connection. Opus is a destructive codec, but at higher bit rates it has proven to compete with audio formats that have much greater delay such as MP3, HE-AAC, and Vorbis.
Recommendations	Suitable for dissemination, but not suitable for archiving.

RealAudio	
File format/extension	RealAudio/ .ra, .ram
Format	A proprietary audio codec developed in 1995 by RealNetworks.
Container/codec	Codec
Description	RealAudio files can use a number of codecs, including RealAudio Lossless Format(ralf). The format was developed in part for streaming media, so users should be aware that some files (for example .ram) are merely links to online files rather than being files themselves.
Recommendations	Not suitable for archiving or dissemination.

Speex	
File format/extension	Speex/ .spx, .ogg
Format	An open, free codec developed by the Xiph.Org Foundation.
Container/codec	Codec
Description	Like other Xiph.Org Foundation formats (for example Vorbis, FLAC), Speex is a free, open codec. Speex is explicitly aimed at providing high quality compressed voice/speech files. Speex is a destructive codec, which means that the compression permanently degrades the quality of the audio file.
Recommendations	Suitable for dissemination, but not suitable for archiving.

Sun AU	
File format/extension	AU/ .au
Format	A format developed by Sun for Unix systems.
Container/codec	Container
Description	As with .wav and .aiff files, Sun AU files tend to be large and of high quality, but do not have wide support outside the UNIX community. Since PCM encoding is mainly used, .au files can also support a number of other codecs.
Recommendations	Does not have broad support outside the UNIX community and is therefore not suitable for archiving.

Waveform Audio	
File format/extension	WAVE, WAV/ .wave, .wav
Format	A widely used, openly documented proprietary format developed by Microsoft and IBM.
Container/codec	Container
Description	The .wav format is commonly used to store uncompressed audio (like PCM) but can also contain audio in various destructive codecs like MP3. The format can also be tagged with metadata and can embed metadata in XMP format. Uncompressed WAV files are large, so sharing WAV files over the internet is rare, but for archiving and audio editing, the format is used in uncompressed form. For more information, read about Broadcast Wave Format.
Recommendations	Suitable for archiving, depending on the codec used.

Windows Media Audio	
File format/ extension	WMA/ .wma, .asf
Format	A proprietary format developed by Microsoft that includes several codecs and a container format.
Container/codec	Codec and container
Description	The WMA collection of codecs includes non-destructive, voice-specific, and 'professional' variants of the standard format. The original version of WMA was developed as a competitor to MP3 and RealAudio. WMA Pro is a newer, more advanced version that supports multi-channel recording and high-resolution audio. WMA Lossless is a lossless, compressive codec and WMA Voice is specialized for voice recordings. In addition, WMA data are often associated with their own ASF container. ⁴⁰
Recommendations	Not suitable for archiving.

⁴⁰ <https://msdn.microsoft.com/en-us/library/ms983668%28loband%29.aspx>. Accessed 12 August 2022